

Speculation on Quantum Mechanics as a Statistical Approximation

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. And S.P.N. Messina Oct.30, 2023

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution has the interesting property that $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2)$ ((A)), but this comes at the price of a canonical distribution and a very large number of particles. Under these circumstances, the MB distribution holds experimentally very well. For lower particle numbers, however, (1) and (2), argue for a power law distribution, namely $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$ (1) and $(E-e)$ power $((n-3)/2)$ (2) for which the property ((A)) does not hold. Thus, the MB distribution is not the full picture for all physical systems.

We argue that quantum mechanics also follows a form similar to ((A)), namely $\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$. We suggest this is associated with circumstances similar to the MB case, namely spatial invariance and steady state- long times. We argue this explains why a quantum bound state includes the tunnelling of a particle and has a wavefunction which exists in all of space. The statistics of quantum mechanics seem to be similar to those of a Maxwell-Boltzmann situation. We argue, however, that like with the power law cases, there may be situations (short time cases) for which the quantum steady state bound solution is not the solution. In other words, we speculate that quantum mechanics may describe a long time steady state solution, with other short time solutions being possible and existing outside of traditional quantum mechanics.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is well-established experimentally for large particle number systems, but this does not mean that it applies in all physical situations. For example, small n cases do not follow a canonical distribution necessarily. Ultimately, the microcanonical approach applies. The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution exhibits the following interesting property:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2) \quad ((1))$$

We argue, however, that ((2)) does not apply to all physical situations. For example, for finite n (particle number), (1) suggests:

$$P(e) = C (E-e) \text{ power } (n-2) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{and} \quad (2), \quad P(e) = C (E-e) \text{ power } ((n-3)/2) \quad ((3))$$

((2)) and ((3)) both exhibit ((1)) for n approaching infinite. In fact, both are Maxwell-Boltzmann like in such a case. As a result, the property ((1)) is found in nature, but does not apply to all physical cases. We ask whether these statistical ideas are at all connected with quantum mechanics.

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics is a statistical type theory which makes use of the Schrodinger equation (in the non-relativistic case) i.e.

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } W(x,t) = H W(x,t) \quad ((4))$$

In the relativistic case, a Klein-Gordon or Dirac equation etc may apply. The point we wish to make is that quantum mechanics makes use of the momentum operator $-i \frac{d}{dx}$ which is associated with the eigenfunction:

$$\exp(i p x) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is a probabilistic entity which follows the Maxwell-Boltzmann type condition((1)), i.e.

$$\exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i (p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((6))$$

We suggest that, like in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, this implies a special kind of statistics. It is not one of large particle number, there is only one particle in a quantum single particle bound state, but rather time is very large and one has a steady state situation. This is why $\exp(ipx)$ exists in all of space. In other words, a so-called quantum bound state is really a steady state situation of a bound particle with tunneling in and out and a wavefunction existing in all of space

Experimentally, the energy eigenstates are accurate. as is the tunnelling. Tunneling, however, may take quite some time and one may ask: Is there a mathematical picture of a quantum bound single particle at early times which do not include tunneling? In other words, is it necessary to always use the steady state, long time, quantum statistical approximation, or could there be short time solutions which lead to different physical results, like the power laws ((2)) and ((3)) above? It seems such solutions should exist and would probably still use the notion of a wavelength, but would not contain probability (i.e. a wavefunction in all of space). One would rather have a localized system with no tunneling yet occurring.

This idea is speculation, but we suggest that quantum mechanics, like the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, may represent a special situation of steady-state long term results. It is possible that these are the results that are usually measured, but there may exist a theory, in addition to steady-state quantum mechanics, which may also physically apply for short term solutions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the property $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2)$ which applies to the experimentally observable Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, does not apply to all physical situations. In particular, there may be power law distributions and microcanonical situations which cannot be approximated by the MB canonical approach.

We suggest that a single particle quantum bound state is a statistical scenario similar to that of the MB situation. In the quantum case, however, it is: $\exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i (p_1+p_2) x)$ which holds. We argue that a quantum bound state is a very special situation, namely one of steady state, long time results. In other words, one does not simply have a bound state, but rather a bound state associated with tunnelling and probability in all of space.

Steady state situations are ones which appear in nature and may be measured, as is shown by the experimental success of quantum mechanics. We speculate, however, that like in the case of power laws which tend to a Maxwell-Boltzmann form in the large n limit, there may be physics, other than the quantum steady state one, which describes single particle bound states before they have time to tunnel.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution from a Microcanonical Power Law Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2023)
2. Lopez-Riuz R. And Calbet Z. Why the Maxwell Distribution is the Attractive Fixed Point of the Boltzmann equation 2006
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/nlin/0611044.pdf>

